

ABSTRACT

Due to the nature of work in microbiology teaching laboratories fomites can easily become contaminated and transmit infectious diseases to users. The aim of this study was to determine the risk of microbial contamination and transmission of pathogens to users of the Accra Technical University Microbiology Teaching Laboratories. Five solid surfaces from the two laboratories including door handles, refrigerator handles, tap handles, student's bench surface and lecturer's bench surfaces were swabbed and cultured onto MacConkey, Nutrient, Mannitol salt and Sabouraud dextrose agar media. Gram negative bacteria were recovered from all sites except the door handles which showed no growth. Microbes recovered were *Staphylococcus aureus* (24.4%), *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (17.2%), *Proteus sp.* (13.8%), *Enterobacter sp.* (6.9%), *Citrobacter sp.* (6.9%), *Salmonella sp.* (6.9%), *Citrobacter freundii* (3.5%) and yeast was (20.7%). Solid surfaces in a microbiology teaching laboratory act as fomites although not all microbes and yeast are clinically significant to immunocompetent persons.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATIONS

MEANING

TSI	Triple Sugar Iron
DLLBS Surface	Down Laboratory Lecturer's Bench
DLSBS Surface	Down Laboratory Student's Bench
DLRH	Down Laboratory Refrigerator Handle
DLTH	Down Laboratory Tap Handle
DLDH	Down Laboratory Door Handle
TLLBS	Top Laboratory Lecturer's Bench Surface
TLSBS	Top Laboratory Student's Bench Surface
TLRH	Top Laboratory Refrigerator Handle
TLTH	Top Laboratory Tap Handle
TLDH	Top Laboratory Door Handle

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND STUDY

Fomites are referred to as inanimate objects which become contaminated with pathogenic bacteria and then spread infection to others (Nworie, Ayeni, Eze, & Azi, 2012). Fomites when in constant contact with humans or natural habitats of pathogenic organisms constitute a major source of spread of infectious diseases (Brooks, Butel, Morse, & Jawetz, 2007). The fomites include door handles, tap handles, student's bench surface, lecturer's bench surface and refrigerator handle.

The hypothesis that microorganisms can cause human diseases are deduced from two facts, firstly, interaction between us and inanimate objects or environment is constant and close, secondly environmental objects are usually contaminated often with important human pathogens (Pyrek, 2002). Even though it is not relatively easy to establish the role microorganisms play in causing human disease, it is fairly easy to assess the prevalence of these organisms in the environment.

Microorganisms are found everywhere, Bacteria and yeast contaminate our body, our houses, work places such as laboratories, and the whole environment. Fortunately, among many billions of bacteria, only 1500 can be dangerous for our health, causing different diseases such as pneumonia or skin infection (Humphrey, Martin, & Whitehead, 1994). A major part of every ecosystem is occupied by microorganisms. In such environments they either live freely or as parasites (Reynolds and Hurst, 2005). Human hands usually harbor microorganisms both as part of body normal flora as well as transient microbes contacted from the environment, it serves as a medium for the propagation of microorganisms from place to place and from person to person (Nworie, 2012).

Students of Accra Technical University have access to service offices regularly for different purposes. Given that the door handles of the Microbiology teaching laboratories are not routinely disinfected, the opportunity for the transmission of contaminating microorganisms is great. Although universal safety precautions, particularly in relation to hand hygiene, are taught to students and routinely practiced by most laboratory users, the possibility that persons at times ignore these precautions when entering or exiting the laboratory, and touching and

decontaminating laboratory solid surfaces does exist (Maier, Pepper, & Gerba, 2009).

These activities may result in diseases ranging from respiratory, enteric, skin and wound infections. Several microorganisms can survive on the surface of fomites for a period of time long enough to be transmitted to hands or other exposed areas of the body. Among these are *Enterococcus faecalis* and *Enterococcus faecium* which can survive on fomites for up to seven days (Bennett, Jarvis, & Brachman, 2007). Because faculty and most laboratory students interact with persons, family and friends, who are not laboratory practitioners, the risk of transmitting potentially pathogenic bacteria to these persons cannot be overlooked. This study is expected to highlight the problem of fomite contamination in the Microbiology teaching laboratories of Accra Technical University.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Fomites such as door handles, tap handles, student and lecturer's benches are mostly used by multiple persons and are not routinely disinfected, the opportunity for the transmission of yeast and contaminating microorganisms is potentially great (Kausar & Nabiha, 2014). The environment significantly influences multiple factors in the chain of infection. Although microbiologically contaminated surfaces including refrigerator handle can serve as reservoirs for pathogens and contribute to the transmission of infections (Bennett, Jarvis, & Brachman, 2007). The present study is aimed at investigating the microbial and yeast contamination of door handles, tap handles, students' bench, lecturer's bench and refrigerator handle in the Microbiology teaching laboratories of Accra Technical University.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTION

Are fomites in the Microbiological teaching laboratories a potential source of transmitting yeast and pathogenic bacteria?

1.4 AIM

To determine the risk of microbial contamination and transmission of pathogens to users of the Microbiology teaching laboratories.

1.5 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- I. To collect swab samples from fomites in the Microbiology teaching laboratories.
- II. To isolate bacteria from collected swab samples by culture.
- III. To identify bacteria isolated from swab samples by Gram stain and biochemical tests.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Role of Fomites in Disease Transmission

Fomites consist of animate or inanimate porous and nonporous surfaces that can become contaminated with pathogenic microorganisms and serve as reservoirs of microbial pathogens and vectors for cross-transmission in the domestic environment and in community settings (Boone & Gerba, 2007). Potential pathogens from sources such as raw foods, infected persons and animals can be transferred between inanimate and animate surfaces through either direct or indirect contact. Environmental surfaces become contaminated with virus, bacteria or parasites shed by infected or colonized individuals by direct contact with body secretions such as blood, feces, urine, saliva, and nasal fluid (Koopmans & Duizer, Foodborne Viruses, 2004), contact with soiled hands, contact with aerosolized virus or bacteria generated by talking, sneezing, coughing, or vomiting (Bellamy, Laban, Barrett, & Talbot, 1998). Surfaces near or in close contact with individuals can even become contaminated from colonized normal skin with *S. aureus*, *Enterococcus faecium* and *faecalis*, *Klebsiella spp.* and with gram-negative bacteria. After a fomite becomes contaminated, the transfer of infectious bacteria easily occur between hand to fomite, fomite to hand, hand to hand, hand to fomite to hand, or fomite to hand to fomite (Sattar, et al., 2001).

2.2 Bacteria on fomites

Several studies have identified bacteria prevalent on environmental surfaces both in domestic environments and in community settings. In a hospital study, it was reported that Vancomycin-Resistant *Enterococci* (VRE) were recovered more frequently from rooms with contaminated surfaces 60-70% in which there was a high proportion of VRE-colonized body sites than from rooms with only a few colonized body sites (Bonten, et al., 1996). It was found that when patients had Methicillin-Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) in a wound or urine, 36% of surfaces were contaminated, while when MRSA was isolated from sputum, blood, or conjunctivae, only 6% of surfaces were contaminated. In the same study, it was reported that environmental contamination of MRSA occurred in rooms of 73% of infected patients and 69% of colonized patients (Boyce, Potter-Bynoe, Chenevert, & King, 1997).

Environmental surveillance studies have investigated the prevalence of nosocomial pathogens in intensive care units (ICUs) and the most commonly reported surfaces to be contaminated with MRSA, VRE, *Enterococcus spp.*, *Enterobacter spp.*, *C. difficile*, and Gram negative rods are the floor next to the bed, bathroom floor, bathroom hand rails, mops, bed linens, patient gowns, healthcare workers (HCWs) gowns or uniforms, gloves, draw sheet, overbed tables, bedside tables/stands, bedside rails, bed sheets, door handle, bedside commodes, toilet seat, toilet rail, keyboard, computer table, faucet, tubs, washbasins, chairs, dresser, nurse call button, TV remote, shelves, cabinet, and window sill (Boyce, Potter-Bynoe, Chenevert, & King, 1997). Inanimate surfaces near or in close contact with affected patients as well as those that are frequently touched by hospital personnel commonly become contaminated with MRSA, VRE, and other pathogens and that the frequency of contamination is affected by the body site at which patients are colonized or infected (Zervos, Kauffman, Therasse, Bergman, Mikesell, & Schaberg, 1987). The evidence that personnel may contaminate their gloves or possibly their hands, by touching surfaces or medical equipment suggests that contaminated environmental surfaces serve as microbial reservoirs and vehicles of transmission in hospitals (Layton, Perez, Heald, & Patterson, 1993). Paper currency used in several countries has been reported to harbor bacteria and parasites including *E. coli*, *B. cereus*, *S. aureus*, and *Salmonella* ranging from (0.1 CFU/cm² to 128 CFU/cm²) and has been identified as a reservoir and vehicle of microbial transmission (Uneke & Ogbu, 2007). Surface contamination has been shown to spread by using cleaning cloths that are harboring viruses and bacteria (Gibson, Crandall, & Ricke, 2012).

2.2.1 Survival of bacteria on fomites and fingers

Both Gram negative and Gram-positive bacteria have been shown to survive on nonporous and porous fomites from a few minutes to several days. (Noskin, Stosor, Cooper, & Patterson, 1995) showed Vancomycin-Resistant *Enterococci* (VRE) to survive on several fomites. They found *E. faecalis* and *E. faecium* surviving 5 days and 7 days on countertops, respectively, 24 hours on bed rails, 60 min on telephone headpiece, and 30 min on the surface of stethoscopes. (Neel & Maley, 2000) reported the survival of MRSA and VRE on five common hospital materials, clothing, towels, scrub suits and lab coats, privacy drapes, and splash aprons to be from 1 day to as long as 90 days. VRE, *E. faecium*, and *E. faecalis* have been shown to survive for at least 60 min on gloved and ungloved fingertips.

2.3 Role of Hands in Disease Transmission

2.3.1 Hands

Multiple studies prove that environmental contamination in the domestic environment and community setting plays an important role in the transmission of microbial pathogens. Epidemiologic data have suggested for more than a century and a half that healthcare workers spread microbes from patient to patient via contaminated hands causing health care associated infections (Werber, Rutala, Miller, Huslage, & Sickbert-Benett, 2010). Touching fomites animate (hands) or inanimate, such as countertops, toys, eating utensils, towels or doorknobs, inadvertently contaminated with secretions, vomit, or nasal mucosa from infected person and then transferring the pathogens from the hands to the eyes, nose or mouth, are further routes of spread. Most documented foodborne viral outbreaks can be traced to food that has been manually handled by an infected food handler (Koopmans & Duizer, 2004).

2.4 Bacterial transmission

There is substantial evidence to show that bacterial transmission occurs in both homes and community settings. Studies have shown that the same strain of gentamicin-resistant *E. faecalis* and MRSA has been isolated in two separate hospitals, suggesting that interhospital spread of gentamicin-resistant *enterococci* may have been caused by transient carriage on the hands of personnel who rotate between the two hospitals or by the transfer of patients from one facility to the other (Zervos, Kauffman, Therasse, Bergman, Mikesell, & Schaberg, 1987). (Muto, et al., 2003) reported that there has even been evidence to suggest transmission of MRSA clones from one city to city, from country to country, and even from continent to continent traced to the transfer of patients infected or colonized with MRSA. The hands of health care workers are a major source of transmission of nosocomial pathogens and frequently acquire transient flora, which colonize the superficial layers of the skin (Reybrouck, 1983). Multiple studies have shown that HCWs hands or gloves frequently acquire multidrug-resistant MRSA, VRE, *Klebsiella spp.*, *C. difficile* and other pathogenic flora during direct contact with patients or contact with contaminated surfaces found in close proximity of infected or colonized patients (Noskin, Stosor, Cooper, & Patterson, 1995). MRSA and VRE have even contaminated gloves of personnel who had no direct contact with patients, but had touched contaminated surfaces (Boyce, Potter-Bynoe, Chenevert, & King, 1997).

2.5 IDENTIFICATION OF BACTERIA PATHOGENS ON FOMITES

The Gram stain is a widely used microbiological staining procedure that greatly aids in the identification and characterization of bacteria. It is one of the differential stains that are used to characterize bacteria into two groups; either gram positive or gram negative bacteria. The gram positive bacteria will typically have a stronger affinity for crystal violet on applying gram's iodine than the gram negative cell wall. Being a mordant, gram's iodine forms a complex with crystal violet in the stain that has attached more tightly to the cell wall of gram positive bacteria than that of the gram negative bacteria. The procedure for the gram staining involves the following.

A test organism was used for gram stain and a drop of saline was added onto the slide and an inoculating loop was to pick a colony from the agar plates and drop onto glass slide to make a smear. The glass slide was air dried. The smear was heat fixed by quickly passing it two –three times through a flame. Again, the smear was flooded with crystal violet solution and allowed to act for 1 minute. The slide was rinsed and flooded with iodine solution and the iodine was allowed to act 1 for one (1) minute. All organisms appeared purple which is a gram positive. Excess iodine was rinsed off and decolorized with alcohol approximately for 5 seconds (time depends on density of specimen). The slide was washed immediately with water. After alcohol decolourization, those organisms that are gram negative are no longer visible. The slide was flooded with counterstain, safranin and waited for 30 seconds to 1 minute and was then rinsed in a gentle and indirect stream of tap water until no color appeared on the effluent and blotted to dry with an absorbent paper. Drop of oil immersion was added to the dried smear and the smear was examined under oil immersion (100x) using a Bright field microscope. Biochemical features play a significant role in the identification of bacteria species based on differences in the biochemical activities of different bacteria. Biochemical tests for identification of bacteria as used in this study are described below (Watt, Rayner, & Harris, 1996).

Indole reaction is performed to help differentiate species of the family *Enterobacteriaceae*. This determines the ability of the organism to split tryptophan molecules into indole (metabolic degradation product of the amino acid tryptophan). Bacteria capable of hydrolyzing and deaminating tryptophan possess the enzyme tryptophanase with the production of Indole, Pyruvic acid and ammonia (Samy & Hamdy, 2012).

Citrate utilization test is one of several techniques used to assist in the identification of *enterobacteriaceae* which is based on the ability of an organism to use citrate as its only sole source of carbon and ammonia as its only source of nitrogen. This is done by first, the inoculum is streaked over the slant of Simmon's citrate agar in a tube and incubated for 24 hours. The medium contains sodium citrate, an ammonium salt and the indicator bromothymol blue. The growth on the slant and the colour to blue of the medium indicates a positive result while no colour change indicates a negative result (MacWilliams, 2009).

Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) agar is used to determine whether a gram negative rod utilizes glucose and lactose or sucrose fermentation and forms hydrogen sulphide (H_2S). It is done with a straight inoculating loop by using it to pick a well isolated colony. Then inoculate by first stabbing the center of the medium to the bottom of the test tube and streaking the surface of the agar slant. The cap of the test tube is left loosely and incubates the test tube for 24 hours in an incubator. If the test organism ferments glucose alone, the entire tube (slant and butt) turns acid yellow which the microorganism will begin to degrade proteins on the agar surface thereby resulting in alkaline end product and a pink slant. Also, if the test organism ferments lactose and (or) sucrose, the entire tube remains yellow. The formation of gas is detected by the presence of cracks or bubbles on the agar. H_2S reacts with ferric ammonia citrate to produce a black end product, ferrous sulphide (De la Maza, Pezzlo, & Baron, 1997).

Catalase is used to demonstrate the presence of catalase, an enzyme that catalyses the release of oxygen from hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). It is used to differentiate those bacteria that produce an enzyme catalase, such as *Staphylococci*, from non-catalase producing bacteria such as *Streptococci*. Normally 3% H_2O_2 is used for the routine culture while 15% H_2O_2 is used for detection of catalase in anaerobes (Ellen, Lance, & Sydney, 1994).

Urease broth is a differential medium that tests the ability of an organism to produce an exoenzyme, called urease, which hydrolyzes urea to ammonia and carbon dioxide. The broth contains two pH buffers, urea, a very small amount of nutrients for the bacteria, and the pH indicator phenol red. Phenol red turns yellow in an acidic environment and fuchsia in an alkaline environment. If the urea in the broth is degraded and ammonia is produced, an alkaline environment is created, and the medium turns pink (MacFaddin, 2000).

The Kligler's Iron Agar test employs a medium for the identification of *Enterobacteriaceae*, based on double sugar fermentation and hydrogen sulphide production. It is recommended for

determination of H₂S production by enteric gram-negative bacilli and for detection of H₂S produced by some strains of *Pseudomonas* (Ewing, 1986).

2.6 GRAM POSITIVE BACTERIA

Gram positive bacteria have a bacterial cell wall with a thick peptidoglycan layer outside their cell membrane. This allows crystal violet to soak in, which is responsible for their purple gram stain. Crystal violet needs to have iodine added to keep it trapped within the peptidoglycan layer. Gram positive bacteria cell wall comprises peptidoglycan, lipid and teichoic acid. The peptidoglycan is a porous cross linked polymer which is responsible for the strength of cell wall and it is composed of three components namely Glycan backbone, Tetra-peptide side chain (Chain of four amino acids) linked to NAM and Peptide cross linkage. The teichoic acid is a water soluble polymer of glycerol or rabatol phosphate and its major surface antigen of gram positive bacteria. It contains about 50% of the dry weight of the cell wall. The lipid is antigenic, and can assist in anchoring the peptidoglycan in the cell membrane. Examples of gram-positive bacteria include *Micrococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus* (Watt, Rayner, & Harris, 1996).

2.7 GRAM NEGATIVE BACTERIA

Gram negative bacteria have a thin cell wall made of peptidoglycan, sandwiched between the cell membrane and a bacterial outer membrane (extra protection made from proteins and lipopolysaccharides – imparting resistance to a few types of antimicrobial substances such as lysozyme). This means that crystal violet does not soak in. Crystal violet is then easily washed out by ethanol even despite addition of iodine, however, a counterstain such as safranin will soak through all these layers into the cell to stain the nucleoid region, thus their gram stain is pink. Their cell wall comprises peptidoglycan, an outer membrane composed of lipids, protein and lipopolysaccharide (LPS). The outer membrane is the structure component of gram negative bacteria. LPS is an endotoxin (bacterial toxins consisting of lipids that are located within a cell) produced by gram negative bacteria. Lipid is antigenic. Examples of gram negative bacteria include *E. coli*, *Klebsiella*, *Salmonella*, *Pseudomonas*, *Shigella* etc. (De la Maza, Pezzlo, & Baron, 1997).

2.8 EFFECT OF SOME MICROBES FOUND ON FOMITES ON THE HUMAN BODY

Escherichia coli also known as *E. coli* is a gram-negative, facultative anaerobic, rod-shaped, coliform bacterium of the genus *Escherichia* that is commonly found in the lower intestine of warm-blooded organisms (endotherms). Most *E. coli* strains are harmless, but some serotypes can cause serious food poisoning in their hosts, and are occasionally responsible for product recalls due to food contamination (Singleton, 1999). The harmless strains are part of the normal microbiota of the gut, and can benefit their hosts by producing vitamin K₂, and preventing colonization of the intestine with pathogenic bacteria, having a symbiotic relationship. *E. coli* is (Boone & Gerba, 2007) expelled into the environment within fecal matter. The bacterium grows massively in fresh fecal matter under aerobic conditions for 3 days, but its numbers decline slowly afterwards (Russell & Jarvis, 2001).

Staphylococcus aureus is a gram-positive, round-shaped bacterium that is a member of the Firmicutes, and it is a usual member of the microbiota of the body, frequently found in the upper respiratory tract and on the skin. It is often positive for catalase and nitrate reduction and is a facultative anaerobe that can grow without the need for oxygen (Masalha, Borovok, Schreiber, Aharonowitz, & Cohen, (December 2001)). Although *S. aureus* usually acts as a commensal of the human microbiota it can also become an opportunistic pathogen, being a common cause of skin infections including abscesses, respiratory infections such as sinusitis, and food poisoning. Pathogenic strains often promote infections by producing virulence factors such as potent protein toxins, and the expression of a cell-surface protein that binds and inactivates antibodies. The emergence of antibiotic-resistant strains of *S. aureus* such as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) is a worldwide problem in clinical medicine. Despite much research and development, no vaccine for *S. aureus* has been approved.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a common encapsulated, gram-negative, rod-shaped bacterium that can cause disease in plants and animals, including humans. A species of considerable medical importance, *P. aeruginosa* is a multidrug resistant pathogen recognized for its ubiquity, it has intrinsically advanced antibiotic resistance mechanisms, and its association with serious illnesses (hospital-acquired infections such as ventilator-associated pneumonia and various sepsis syndromes) (Balcht & Smith, 1994). The organism is considered opportunistic insofar as serious infection often occurs during existing diseases or conditions – most notably cystic fibrosis and traumatic burns. It generally affects the immunocompromised but can also infect

the immunocompetent as in hot tub folliculitis. Treatment of *P. aeruginosa* infections can be difficult due to its natural resistance to antibiotics. When more advanced antibiotic drug regimens are needed, adverse effects may result (Itah & Essien, 2005).

It is citrate, catalase, and oxidase positive. It is found in soil, water, skin flora, and most man-made environments throughout the world. It thrives not only in normal atmospheres, but also in low-oxygen atmospheres, thus has colonized many natural and artificial environments. It uses a wide range of organic material for food; in animals, its versatility enables the organism to infect damaged tissues or those with reduced immunity. The symptoms of such infections are generalized inflammation and sepsis.

Klebsiella spp. are gram-negative, non-motile, rod-shaped bacteria that belong to the family *Enterobacteriaceae*. The outermost layer of *Klebsiella spp.* consist of a large polysaccharide capsule that encases the entire cell surface and accounts for the large appearance of the organism. *Klebsiella spp.* have been identified as colonizing hospital patients, where spread is associated with the frequent handling of patients. On rare occasions may cause infections, such as destructive pneumonia (Ainsworth, 2004). Faeces are the most significant course of patient infection; contact with contaminated equipment in hospitals (catheters, I.V. etc, respiratory devices).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 SANITATION AUDIT

A structured sanitation questionnaire was used to conduct a sanitation audit of the conditions in the Microbiology teaching laboratories. Refer to Appendix A.

3.2 SAMPLING SITE

The Microbiology teaching laboratory which happens to be one of the busiest laboratories within Accra Technical University are the locations at which the fomite for this work will be obtained. The Microbiology laboratory is a teaching laboratory that houses 60 students at a time for 3 hours' lecture and 150 students in a day. Activities such as culturing of microorganisms, preparing of smears, keeping non-edible substances, storage of media, refrigeration of pathogenic microorganisms etc make the laboratory a potential source of infections. Hence, the fomites for this work was obtained at the Microbiology teaching laboratory.

3.3 MATERIALS AND EQUIPMENTS

Test tubes, Permanent marker, Incubator, Measuring cylinder, Glass Petri dishes, Universal bottles, Bijoux bottles, Autoclave, Nutrient Agar, MacConkey Agar, Peptone water, Mannitol Salt Agar, Sabouraud Dextrose Agar, Triple Sugar Iron Agar, Simmons Citrate Agar, Hydrogen Peroxide, Urea Broth, Kovac's Indole reagent, Hot Air Oven, Lamina flow, 70% Ethanol, Spatula, Beaker, Conical flask, Weighing balance, Bunsen burner, Swab sticks, Gloves, Cotton, Pasteur pipette.

3.4 SAMPLE COLLECTION

Ten (10) sterile swab samples were collected from the door handles, tap handles, student's bench surfaces, lecturer's bench surfaces and refrigerator handles. Each surface was swabbed with sterile H₂O moistened cotton swab and locked back into its coded case. Swabs from sampled surfaces were aseptically cut into 20 ml of peptone water. This was swirled around and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

After 24 hours, the peptone water was swirled around and a sterile loop was used to collect and inoculate the peptone broth culture on to the Nutrient, Mannitol salt, MacConkey and Sabouraud dextrose agar plates. The plates were turned upside-down and incubated at 35°C for 24 hours in ambient air for nutrient, MacConkey and Mannitol salt agar but Sabouraud dextrose agar plates were incubated for 48 hours due to the slow growth of yeast.

3.5 LABORATORY ANALYSIS

3.5.1 Identification of Isolates

Bacteria isolated were identified by biochemical test which includes indole, citrate, catalase, urease, Triple Sugar Iron test (TSI).

3.5.1.1 Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) Tests

Slopes of TSI were prepared in sterile test tubes as recommended by the manufacturer. A sterile inoculation needle was used to streak the slant with the test organism first and then the butt was stabbed. It was incubated overnight. If the test organism ferments glucose alone, the entire tube (slant and butt) turns acid (yellow); however, the microorganisms will begin to degrade proteins on the agar surface, resulting in alkaline end product and a pink slant. If the test organism ferments lactose (or) sucrose, the entire tube remains yellow. The formation of gas is detected by cracks or bubbles in the agar. H₂S reacts with ferric ammonium citrate to produce a black end product, ferrous sulphide (De la Maza, Pezzlo, & Baron, 1997).

3.5.1.2 Citrate Utilization Test

Slopes of Simmon's citrate agar were prepared as recommended by the manufacturer. A sterile needle was used to streak the slant with the test organism first and then the butt was stabbed. It was incubated for twenty-four (24) hours. A bright blue colour change with microbial growth appeared which indicated a positive result. No colour change with or without growth indicated a negative result (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3.5.1.3 Indole Test

An inoculation loop was used to pick an isolated colony from the plate aseptically. The colony was then inoculated into peptone water aseptically and incubated for forty-eight (48) hours. After incubation, four or five (4-5) drops of Kovac's indole reagent (paradimethylaminobenzaldehyde or paradimethylaminocinnamaldehyde) was added to the

inoculum. The formation of a red or pink-red ring appeared on the surface which indicated a positive test. No colour change occurs in a negative test (Samy & Hamdy, 2012).

3.5.1.4 Urease Test

An inoculation loop was used to pick an isolated colony from the plate aseptically. The colony was then incubated into urea broth aseptically and incubated for twenty-four (24) hours.

A pink colour change with microbial growth appeared which indicated a positive result. No colour change with or without microbial growth indicated negative results (MacFaddin, 2000).

3.4.1.5 Catalase Test

A small amount of bacterial colony was transferred aseptically onto the surface of a clean, dry glass slide using a loop. A drop of 3% hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) was placed onto the slide and mix. A positive result was the rapid evolution of oxygen (within 5-10 seconds) as evidenced by bubbling. The lack of catalase is evident by lack of or weak bubble production (Ellen, Lance, & Sydney, 1994).

3.5 DATA ANALYSIS

All data was recorded in a log book and entered into Microsoft Office Excel. Data was analyzed descriptively using excel spreadsheet application for grouping of categorical data.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 RESULTS

4.1.1 Sanitation Audit

Sanitation and Environmental conditions in the Microbiology teaching laboratories of Accra Technical University have good hygienic systems, due to the fact that the laboratories are cleaned on a regular basis, with good drainage and enough dust bins, but lacks enough towels. There are mops available in case of water spillage in the laboratories and disinfectant for disinfecting the work stations.

Table 1: Sanitation audits in the Microbiology teaching laboratories

Items	Audits	Frequency (%)
Soap provided	Yes	2 (100%)
	No	0 (0%)
Type of soap	Liquid	2 (100%)
	Bar	0 (0%)
Water flowing	Yes	2 (100%)
	No	0 (0%)
Paper towels	Yes	0 (0%)
	No	0 (0%)
Excess storage of waste	Yes	0 (0%)
	No	2 (100%)
General cleanliness	Good	2 (100%)
	Average	0 (0%)
	Bad	0 (0%)

4.1.2 Prevalence of bacteria and yeast presence on sampled fomite

Microbial and yeast examination was carried out on five different fomites from both microbiology teaching laboratories. These fomites were categorized as: (1) Door handles; (2) Refrigerator handles; (3) Tap handles; (4) Lecturer's bench surfaces; and (5) Student bench surfaces. Table 1 displays 23 bacterial strains that were isolated from the five fomites, of which 3 strains were from the door handles, 5 from the refrigerator handles, 4 from the tap handles, 5 from the lecturer's bench surfaces and 6 from the student's bench surfaces. Among the isolated bacteria contaminants, *Staphylococcus aureus* had the highest prevalence (24.14%), followed by *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (17.24%), *Proteus sp.* (13.79%), *Enterobacter sp.* (6.90%), *Citrobacter sp.* (6.90%), *Salmonella sp.* (6.90%) and *Citrobacter freundii* (3.44%). Of all tested organisms, (41.38%) were gram positive bacteria and (37.93%) were gram negative. The yeast strains that were also isolated from the five fomites, of which 1 strain was from the door handles, 2 from the refrigerator handles, none from the tap handles, 2 from the lecturer's bench surfaces and 1 from the student's bench surfaces. Among the isolated pathogens, yeast constituted (20.69%) of the contaminants isolated in this study.

The student's bench surface recorded the highest prevalence while the door knobs/handles recorded the least, this is because it is being used by most students. This situation calls for awareness creation concerning the types of bacteria isolated from it and its potency or threat to human health life.

Table 2: Prevalence of bacteria and yeast isolated from different fomites in the microbiology teaching laboratories.

Bacteria	Door handles n(%)	Refrigerator handles n(%)	Tap handles n(%)	Lecturer's bench n(%)	Student's bench n(%)	Total N(%)
Gram positive						
<i>S. aureus</i>	1 (25)	-	2 (50)	2 (28.5)	2 (28.5)	7 (24.4)
<i>S. epidermidis</i>	1 (25)	1 (14.3)	-	1 (14.3)	2 (28.5)	5 (17.2)
Gram negative						
<i>Enterobacter sp.</i>	-	-	-	1 (14.3)	1 (14.3)	2 (6.9)
<i>Citrobacter sp.</i>	-	-	1 (25)	-	1 (14.3)	2 (6.9)
<i>Salmonella sp.</i>	-	1 (14.3)	1 (25)	-	-	2 (6.9)
<i>C.freundii</i>	-	1 (14.3)	-	-	-	1 (3.5)
<i>Proteus sp.</i>	1 (25)	2 (28.5)	-	1 (14.3)	-	4 (13.8)
Yeast	1 (25)	2 (28.5)	-	2 (28.5)	1 (14.3)	6 (20.7)
Total	4 (100)	7 (100)	4 (100)	7 (100)	7 (100)	29(100)

4.1.3 Prevalence of microorganisms in the two microbiology teaching laboratories.

In this study, there were seven (7) types of bacteria isolated from 10 swab samples from fomites, which were collected from the microbiology teaching laboratories of Accra Technical University. The bacteria isolates found were *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Enterobacter sp.*, *Citrobacter sp.*, *Salmonella sp.*, *Citrobacter freundii* and *Proteus sp.* Pathogenic microbes recovered from cultures of different items in the ground floor microbiology teaching laboratory swab specimens included *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus sp.*, *Citrobacter sp.*, *Citrobacter freundii* and *Enterobacter sp.* while there was yeast growth on all the fomites samples except the tap handle. The highest bacteria prevalence count was *Staphylococcus aureus*, found on all the fomites except refrigerator handle while the lowest count were *Citrobacter sp.*, and *Citrobacter freundii* which were found on the tap handle and refrigerator handle respectively.

It also shows the total bacterial and yeast counts from different items in the first floor microbiology teaching laboratory. Pathogenic bacteria recovered from swab samples included *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus sp.*, *Salmonella sp.*, and *Citrobacter sp.* while there was yeast growth only on the refrigerator and lecturer's bench surface. *Staphylococcus aureus* recorded the highest prevalence which was found on all the fomites except the refrigerator and door handles. *Citrobacter sp.* was the least prevalent and was found only on the student's bench surface.

Figure 1: Frequency of bacteria and yeast isolated from fomite samples

4.2 DISCUSSION

In this study, fomites in the Microbiology teaching laboratories are a potential source of transmitting yeast and pathogenic bacteria. There were seven (7) types of bacteria isolated from ten (10) swab samples from fomites, which were collected from the two microbiology teaching laboratories of Accra Technical University.

From the findings in the study the ground floor microbiology laboratory was known to have more bacteria isolates and yeast contaminants compared to that of the first floor. This is because the ground floor microbiology laboratory is mostly used for lectures and bacteria culturing. This causes the rapid increase in bacteria and yeast growth. According to the findings of (Kloos & Bannerman, 1994), Bacterial isolates such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella species*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Klebsiella pneumonia* are one of the most common pathogens that can be found in most contaminated sites and can cause infections that can increase the risk of adverse outcome.

According to the findings of (Noskin, Stosor, Cooper, & Patterson, 1995), numerous studies have also reported that various bacteria can adhere and survive on hands, clothes and currencies for hours, days or weeks after initial contact with microorganism. As shown in (table 1), one to six different organisms were detected on the fomites. This study revealed that, there was a high level of bacterial and yeast contaminants on the microbiology teaching laboratories fomites which were contaminated with considerable number of Gram positive and Gram negative, this indicated that there was high prevalence of pathogenic bacteria in the microbiology teaching laboratories of Accra Technical Laboratory. These microorganisms could be transferred from contaminated surfaces to hand via surface to surface cross examination or any sort of direct pathways such as door knobs/handles, tap handles and others, subsequently, these microorganisms could be inhaled if adequate hygiene practices are not applied.

In this study, *Staphylococcus aureus* was isolated from all the fomites samples except the refrigerator samples and this bacterial isolate is of medical importance as a causative agent of human diseases. It has been known to cause various pus-forming infections in humans such as boils, carbuncles, impetigo, osteomyelitis, toxic-shock syndrome (Hartman, 2004). On the other hand, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* which was also isolated from most of the samples is a

normal habitat of the skin but can occasionally assume an opportunistic pathogenic role in causing human infection such as endocarditis.

In humans, multiple *Enterobacter species* are known to act as opportunistic pathogens (disease-causing organisms), including *E. cloacae*, *E.aerogenes*, *E. gergoviae* and *E. agglomerans*. Pathogenic *Enterobacter* can cause any of a variety of conditions, including eye and skin infections, meningitis, bacteremia (bacterial blood infection), pneumonia and urinary tract infections. The most common site of infection by *Citrobacter freundii* is the biliary tract. The most dangerous disease caused by *Citrobacter freundii* is neonatal meningitis. This is an inflammation of the meninges (the system of membranes that surround the central nervous system) due to an invasion of bacteria. All previous studies highlight the severe health impacts originating from microorganisms like the ones found in this study; and subsequently, extensive efforts to minimize their occurrences are required.

There are several important factors that influence the survival of bacterial cells on surfaces; these include characteristics of an organism and its surrounding environment. The existence of specific surface structures such as pili, flagella and extracellular polysaccharides have been suggested to affect the adhesion and survival of bacteria (Peng, Tsai, & Chou, 2001). Numerous studies have reported that various bacteria can adhere and survive on hands, utensils, sponges, cloths and currency for hours, days or weeks after initial contact with the microorganism (Scott & Bloomfield, 1990).

Transmission of pathogens takes place by either direct or indirect pathways. Direct pathways include human-to-human transmissions, such as hand-shaking (Ulger, Esen, & Dilek, 2009). As shown in (Figure 1), different microorganisms were detected on different fomites. These microorganisms could transfer from contaminated surfaces to hands via surface-surface cross contamination or any sort of direct pathways. Subsequently, these microorganisms could be ingested or inhaled if adequate hygiene practices are not applied.

Indirect transmission occurs when a non-living agent is involved in the transfer of the pathogen to a susceptible individual such as through air, food, water and inanimate objects known as fomites. It was previously reported that bacteria could adhere to particles of grain dust, which are considered an effective aerosol because its organic materials offer necessary nutrients for airborne microorganisms' adherent to their surfaces (Wada-kura, Maxwell, & Sadiq, 2009).

Microorganisms found in contaminated surfaces in this study (Figure 1), if transferred via any media suggested above and ingested or inhaled by humans could cause severe health problems like those reported in the above discussion. Overall, results in this study highlight the threat posed by contaminated surfaces if cross-contamination occurs followed by ingestion or inhalation.

This study confirms that various inanimate objects in the microbiology teaching laboratories of Accra Technical University associated directly or indirectly with fomites were variously contaminated with known bacterial and yeast pathogens. Although the direct involvement of these fomites in disease transmission was not investigated in this study, the isolation of these pathogens presents a serious concern for possible nosocomial transmission.

Some researchers (Kramer et al, 2006) concluded in their study that the common nosocomial pathogens may survive or persist on surfaces for months and can thereby be a continuous source of transmission if no regular prevention surface disinfection is performed. Although a researcher (Ayiliffe, 1991) remarked the inanimate environment has little relevance to the spread of infection, other workers (Prescott, Harley, & Klein, 1999) noted that the fomites are involved in the transmission of pathogens in health care environments.

The results from this study in which established bacterial and yeast pathogens were isolated from fomites agrees with the findings of some of the workers (Orji, et al, 2005) but varies with the report of other researchers (Njoku-Obi & Ojiegbe, 1993) who did not find any pathogenic bacteria on fomites from their study.

The presence of yeast as seen in this study confirms the contamination of air from outside of the microbiology teaching laboratories. This same observation was made by some researchers (Njoku-Obi & Ojiegbe., 1993). In the present study, it was observed that the infection rate in the different microbiological teaching laboratories correspond with the level of contamination of fomites observed. Pathogens isolated from this study can affect results of cultures set up in the laboratory by giving false results and can also prove costly as projects would take the challenge of dealing with contamination of their cultures.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, results obtained from this study have shown that there is presence of pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Proteus sp.*, *Enterobacter sp.*, *Citrobacter sp.*, *Salmonella sp.* and *Citrobacter freundii*. This study shows that frequently or heavily used fomites harbor highly pathogenic yeast and bacteria, which potentially can cause serious diseases in the near future. The finding of established bacterial and yeast pathogens on fomites poses danger to the students, lecturers and other visitors and if they eventually find their way as etiologic agents of infection. It will be necessary to establish regular surface cleaning intervention as part of effective infection control policy in the microbiology teaching laboratories.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

It is therefore recommended that sanitary conditions of our laboratories should be improved. The fomites should be disinfected regularly and laboratory users should wash their hands with detergent or any other antiseptic agent before and after using the laboratory. It is imperative to conduct regular testing to check for bacterial and yeast contamination and increase community awareness and education for hygienic standards.

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APPENDIX A

Media Preparations

Nutrient Agar, Simmons Citrate Agar, Urea Broth, MacConkey Agar, Mannitol Salt Agar, Peptone water, Triple Sugar Iron Agar, Sabouraud Dextrose Agar was prepared from dehydrated powder according to the manufacturer's instructions.

6.5g of Sabouraud dextrose agar in 100 ml of distilled water was measured separately into clean conical flask allowed to dissolve completely by heating and corked with cotton immediately and labeled.

11.1g of Mannitol salt agar in 100 ml of distilled water was measured separately into clean conical flask allowed to dissolve completely by heating and corked with cotton immediately and labeled.

2.8g of Nutrient agar in 100 ml of distilled water was measured separately into clean conical flask allowed to dissolve completely by heating and corked with cotton immediately and labeled.

11g of MacConkey agar in 200 ml of distilled water was measured separately into clean conical flask allowed to dissolve completely by heating and corked with cotton immediately and labeled.

These were autoclaved at 15lbs pressure (121°C) for 15 minutes, allowed to cool and dispensed into sterile petri dishes for use before solidifying.

6.5g of TSI agar in 100 ml of distilled water was measured separately into a clean conical flask allowed to dissolve completely by heating. Using a measuring cylinder 10ml of the TSI was measured into ten (10) sterile test tubes.

3.7g of Simmons citrate agar in 150ml of distilled water was measured separately into conical flask allowed to dissolve completely by heating. Using a measuring cylinder 15ml of the simmons citrate agar was measured into ten (10) sterile universal bottles.

3g of peptone powder in 200 ml distilled water was measured separately in a clean conical flask and stirred properly to dissolve to avoid particles of the peptone water. Using a measuring cylinder 20 ml of the peptone water was measured into ten (10) sterile bijoux bottles.

These were then autoclaved at 15lbs pressure (121°C) for 15 minutes.

8.15g of Urea broth in 200 ml distilled water was measured separately into conical flask and stirred properly to dissolve to avoid particles of the urea broth and filtered. It was not

autoclaved. Using measuring cylinder 20 ml urea broth was measured into ten (10) sterile universal bottles.

APPENDIX B

Table 3: Biochemical test for gram negative bacteria

Biochemical test								
TSI								
Sample Code	Glucose	Lactose	Gas	H ₂ S	Indole	Citrate	Urea	Identity
DL SBS 2	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	<i>Enterobacter sp.</i>
DL RH 2	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	<i>C. freundii</i>
DL SBS 2	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	<i>Enterobacter sp.</i>
DL TH 2	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	<i>Citrobacter sp.</i>
TL TH 1	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Salmonella sp.</i>
TL RH 1	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Salmonella sp.</i>
TL SBS 1	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	<i>Citrobacter sp.</i>
TL SBS 1	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	<i>Proteus sp.</i>

Table 4: Showing characteristics of Isolates from swab sticks.

ISOLATES	MEDIA		
	MacConkey Agar	MANNITOL SALT AGAR	NUTRIENT AGAR
<i>S. aureus</i>	Pale pink	Yellow or white colonies	Yellow colonies
<i>S. epidermidis</i>	-	Pink colonies	-
<i>Proteus sp.</i>	Swarming motility	Yellow or white colonies Swarming motility	Swarming motility

APPENDIX C

GALLERY

TSI Test

Presence of growth on MacConkey agar

Indole test

Citrate test

Growth on Mannitol salt agar

Growth on Sabouraud dextrose agar